

THE INTERPLAY OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND SPIRITUAL HERITAGE

ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА И ДУХОВНОГО НАСЛЕДИЯ

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Keywords: Spiritual heritage refers to universal spiritual wealth of the past and present, which is spiritually valuable, leaves an indelible mark, lives forever, serves all social interests and needs, and serves goodness. Spiritual heritage is manifested as a spiritual value, which includes science, including philosophy, literature, art, ethics, religious and secular teachings, superstition, etc. Spiritual heritage does not lose its value with the passage of time, but acquires a new meaning and significance in terms of quality.

Abstract: In this article, the concept of spiritual heritage is given a broader definition, touching on the roots of our spirituality, it is discussed about their role in the destiny of the past, present and future generations. Spirituality, spiritual heritage, value, tradition.

Spiritual heritage is a product of spiritual development, created by human intelligence, capable of leading the next generation towards good development, contributing to the growth of people's consciousness and worldview, and their efforts to learn and master the world. a concept that represents a set of age-old values passed down from generation to generation from empowering ancestors. The spiritual heritage can belong to a single person, a separate group or representatives of a specific nation, depending on the significance of the experience of the ancestors, the spiritual wealth left by them in the practical activities and way of thinking of future generations. According to the fact that they are created in a certain national language, they reflect national cultural and spiritual

traditions, views, they are related to the nation, according to the fact that they cover different nationalities living in a certain area, to society, according to the fact that a certain state authority acts. It can also be characteristic of a state according to the time it was created, and a civilization according to its high place in the history of mankind. Also, the spiritual heritage can belong to the nation, state, region and the whole world at the same time. For example, the religious and educational heritage of Imam Bukhari and Imam Tirmidhi, Abu Ali ibn Sina's medical discoveries or Mirza Ulughbek's astronomical discoveries, not only the peoples living in our nation and region, but also the world civilization and culture, are priceless spiritual treasures. is an inheritance.

Spiritual heritage, unlike material heritage, is valuable because it creates wide opportunities to understand the intellectual and psychological states, actions, practical activities and their results that happened, are giving or can give in the world and in the inner world of a person. At the same time, spiritual heritage cannot be contrasted with material heritage. Because the material heritage that has reached us can become a spiritual heritage at the same time in terms of its influence on the human mind. For example, although historical monuments created in the distant past that have reached us belong to material heritage, they become spiritual heritage according to their engineering, decorative works, construction history and the preparation of related materials, creators and other aspects. Similarly, although technologies and equipment for the production of material goods belong to material heritage, the transmission of traditions in this regard from ancestors to generations is carried out in the form of spiritual heritage. From this point of view, many natural skills of mankind, which are not reflected in written sources, are passed down from ancestors to generations in the form of spiritual heritage. The emergence of writing is considered the greatest achievement of mankind in the way of preservation and enrichment of spiritual heritage. Thanks to the writing, information about human development, including more than five thousand years of history of spiritual heritage, several million years of Earth and space bodies, has been collected in modern science.

Enriching, developing, directing people to new ideological directions by influencing people's mind, inner world, way of thinking, feelings represents the true essence of spiritual heritage. Also, today, the importance of spiritual heritage as a value that deeply affects the way of life of people is becoming more and more evident. Ideological, ideological, educational, cultural, religious and moral values, worldview, customs, traditions and relations in the thinking of the society determine the spiritual heritage of the future generation. Cultural values and spiritual heritage have served as a powerful source of spirituality for our people for thousands of years. Despite the strong ideological pressure that lasted for a long time, the people of Uzbekistan managed to preserve their historical and cultural values and unique traditions that have been passed down from generation to

generation. From the first days of our independence, the restoration of the huge, priceless spiritual and cultural heritage created by our ancestors over many centuries has become an extremely important task that has risen to the level of state policy. Uzbekistan's own way of renewal and development is based on four main principles from the point of view of spiritual heritage. These principles are: commitment to universal values; restoration, strengthening and development of the spiritual heritage of our people; free expression of one's capabilities; patriotism.

The whole world recognizes that the territory called Uzbekistan, that is, our Motherland, was one of the cradles of civilization not only of the East, but also of the whole world. From this ancient and blessed soil, great scholars, noble scholars, scholars, politicians, and generals have grown. The foundations of religious and worldly sciences were created and polished on this land. The complex water structures built before and after BC, and the monuments that have not lost their beauty and prestige to this day, testify to the high level of farming, handicraft culture, architecture and urban planning in our country since ancient times. From the oldest petroglyphs and inscriptions, which have survived the trials of barbarism, to more than 20,000 manuscripts stored in our libraries today, they embody history, literature, art, politics, ethics, philosophy, medicine, mathematics, physics, chemistry, astronomy, Tens of thousands of works related to architecture and agriculture are our incomparable spiritual wealth and pride. A nation with such a great heritage is rare in the world. To preserve the true spiritual heritage of our people, such as faith, honesty, kindness, concern, honor, respect for elders, honor for children, hospitality, loyalty to the country and the people, instilling in the blood of the future generation. if it is said that the society should always gain priority in its daily life, first of all, the need to work in close cooperation and harmony with religious people and religious leaders should be taken into account. The role of religious scholars is clearly visible in mastering the spiritual heritage, which represents values related to spiritual purification, moral education, thinking about the peace of the world, peaceful activities and maintaining the harmony of nations. In addition, the people of our country have been in close contact with the people known to them since ancient times. There are many examples of this. The Great Silk Road leading from the depths of Asia to the Middle East, Europe and Africa, scientists and thinkers known to the entire cultural world, the creativity of our great ancestors, who are the creators of states and cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Shahrissabz, Khiva. delivered a spiritual legacy that has surprised everyone with its wealth and beauty.

It can be emphasized that the pure spirit and traditions of our ancestors, our best traditions, revival of our spiritual heritage are important factors for the success of reforms and the development of our country. It is known that over the centuries, the noble qualities of our people, such as high spirituality, justice, and love of

enlightenment, have developed organically with the teachings of Eastern philosophy and Islam. On the other hand, these philosophical and moral teachings were enriched by the genius of our people. Our spiritual heritage that is being created today is formed in accordance with this philosophy in accordance with the wise thoughts of our ancestors thinkers such as Khwaja Ahmad Yasavi, Khwaja Bahauddin Naqshband, Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulughbek, Alisher Navoi, Babur Mirza. must The people of Uzbekistan are proud of a huge spiritual heritage built up over thousands of years. Unique historical monuments of Samarkand, Tashkent, Bukhara, Khiva, Shahrisabz, Termiz, Great Eastern thinkers al-Bukhari, al-Tirmizi, Ahmad Yassavi, Bahauddin Naqshband, al-Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Muhammad Khorezmi, Ahmad Farghani, Alisher The works of Navoi, Mirzo Ulug'bek, Babur have become the priceless property of all humanity. The historical spirit of the people is awakening, the eyes of spirituality are being opened, thanks to this, the feelings of national pride and love for the motherland are developing in the hearts of people. Beruni, Ibn Sina, Khorezmi, Farghani, Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Bahauddin Naqshband, Amir Temur, Mirza Ulughbek, Babur, Pahlavon Mahmud, Sultan Weiss, Nasiruddin Rabguzi, Suleiman Bakirghani, Bahauddin Valad and like his great son Jalaluddin Rumi, Abulqasim Ali Khorazmi, Ismail Jurjani, Sirojiddin Sakkoki, Munis, Ogahi, Bayani, Safo Mughanni, Chokar, Shirozi, Hajikhan, Bolabakhshi, Abdullah Qadiri, Cholpon, Fitrat, Behbudi, Usman Nasir The return to the nation of the spiritual heritage - eternity - of tens and hundreds of great children was one of the brightest achievements of independent Uzbekistan. Accordingly, it can be said that any society cannot imagine its future without developing and strengthening its spiritual potential, spiritual and moral values in the minds of people. Customs, traditions, folklore, science, literature, art and other spiritual heritage are important.

References :

1. Karimov High spirituality is an invincible force. 2008. "Spiritual"
2. Boboyeva H. and others Basics of cultural studies.-T. 2001

3. Tulenov J. Philosophy of values. -T. "Uzbekistan", 1998

4. Khairullayeva M. From the history of social philosophical thoughts in Uzbekistan. -T. "Uzbekistan", 1995

5. Problems of culture and spirituality.-T.; "Heritage", 1994

. J. Mustafayev. Our rich historical heritage and youth spirituality. SamQXI. Collection of scientific proverbs, 2009. -B. 143.

6. J. Mustafayev. The importance of aesthetic values in the development of the spiritual and moral perfection of a person. SamQXI. Collection of scientific proverbs, April 24-25, 2013, p. 188.

7. J. Mustafayev. Development of science and technology in the 21st century and their impact on social life. Proceedings of the international scientific and practical conference, Problems of introducing innovative technologies in agriculture, SamQXI, 2012, 240 pages.

8. J. Mustafayev Jadidchilik and their importance in improving the development of independent Uzbekistan. The 18th multidisciplinary scientific conference of the Republic on the topic "Scientific-practical research in Uzbekistan". 2020 year. July Part 2. 50 pages.

9. J. Mustafayev. The Emergence Of Jadidism And The Period Of Mahmudkhoja Behbudi's Activity. Published in International Journal of Research (IJR) with ISSN 2348-6848, (Online) and 2348-795X (Print), Vol. 7 Issue 5 Month May Year 2020, India. Impact Factor 5.60, The journal is indexed, peer reviewed and listed in UGC Care. Page: 450

10. J. Mustafayev. The role of Mahmudhoja Behbudi in the formation and development of the Jadidist movement in Turkestan. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. 2020, No. 8.

11. J. Mustafayev. Modernism and the third renaissance. Republican scientific conference on "Succession in spiritual heritage and its role in 21st century education". May 20, 2021. Samarkand.

12. J. Mustafayev. Moral issues in the oldest written monuments of Central Asia. Republican scientific conference on "Succession in spiritual heritage and its role in 21st century education". May 20, 2021. Samarkand.

